

The devastating effects of neoplasia in the vulnerable childhood

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ABSTRACT Cancer accounts for 20% of the causes of death and occupies the second place as a reason of mortality after cardiovascular disease, but the incidence of childhood cancer is little (less than 1% of new cases in western populations). However, in many countries, it is the second or third cause of death in children. All around the world, the main reasons causing death in children are accidents and inadequate nutrition. In countries where this trend has declined, cancer has become the leading cause of death in this young population. Almost 50% of malignancies occur in children aged 0-5 years. Today, cancer is considered a threatening disease for both children and adolescents, but not always fatal. However, not only is it essential to cure the biological cognition but also the psychological (i.e. to know that the child or teenager has cancer) and the social aspect (the reintegration of the child and adolescent into society without stigma). The scope of this study is to investigate the current clinical and psychological management of young patients and children to reintegrate children and adolescents into social life smoothly.

KEYWORDS cancer; children; stress; fear; management; adolescents

Introduction

Significant improvements in life expectancy have been achieved in children and adolescents with cancer. Between 1975 and 2010, childhood cancer mortality decreased by more than 50% with the right treatment, the rates of cure can be as high as 80%, as it has been shown in high-income societies. Survival rates of children with cancer are high, at almost 80% in high-income countries. More than 80% of all childhood cancer cases occur in low and middle-income countries. Although nearly 175000 cancer cases are diagnosed in children younger than 15 years of age, unfortunately, fewer than 40% of childhood cancers are diagnosed or receive early and effective treatment [1]. Delay in early diagnosis is a result of similarity in signs and symptoms of childhood cancers and common diseases in young children [2].

Cancer in children and adolescents

In children, cancer manifests itself more often as a systemic disease rather than as a solid tumour. Another difference is that solid tumours of childhood are mainly blasts and sarcomas, while epithelial-type cancer is rare. Two of the most prominent human oncogenic viruses are hepatitis B virus (HBV) and human papillomavirus (HPV). HBV infection has been preventable by vaccination since 1982; vaccination of neonates and infants is highly effective, resulting in decreased rates of new infections, chronic liver disease and hepatocellular carcinoma [3]. Human papillomavirus (HPV), a sexually transmitted infection, can cause warts and some cancers. Epidemiology and pathology of ovarian tumours in the pediatric population differ from those of women. Abdominal pain was the most predominant symptom in the non-malignant lesion group [4].

Wilm's tumour

We now know other cases of cancer whose aetiology is based on the lack of both normal alleles of an oncogenic gene. One example is Wilm's cancer, a child's kidney cancer that affects one in 10,000 children who are born. Wilm's cancer cases account for 5% of all cancers in children. Both sporadic and familial cases

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DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.neoplasia-childhood

First Received: September 03, 2018

Accepted: December 26, 2018

Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG)

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have been reported. In its hereditary form, Wilm's cancer is transmitted as an autosomal dominant feature with a variety of expressions [5-6].

Retinoblastoma

Until 1850, retinoblastoma was a lethal childhood cancer. The slow progress of this cancer was the result of a gradual brain injury. The discovery of the microscope (1850, Herman von Helmholtz), made it possible to perform early surgical excision before its spread to neighbouring tissues with fatal results. At the same time, its family dependence was also known. Young people with a hereditary defective gene are healthy but have an increased risk of developing cancer. Since the presence of a single normal Rb gene is enough for a person to be healthy, it is believed that this is a residual disease. Because individuals with a mutated allele of the Rb gene transfer it on average to half of their children, cloning of this gene allows prenatal diagnosis of the disease. By the use of this method, risk assessment can be carried out for retinoblastoma in the fetus before birth [7-8].

Pigmentary dry skin

In 1968, James Cleaver, studying a medical article on patients with sun-sensitive hypersensitivity, discovered that the cells derived from these patients are unable to eliminate ultraviolet radiation damage to the DNA. This disease is called pigmented dry skin disease and is characterised by extreme skin sensitivity in exposure to sunlight, occurring mainly in the early years of life. The parts of the skin exposed to sunlight are covered with dye stains, and skin lesions develop into malignant tumours.

The prognosis is bleak for these patients, and death generally happens between the 20th and 25th year of age. Based on this disease, it has been shown that the persistence of DNA damage to human cells, caused by exposure to the sun, is directly linked with the onset of cancers [9].

Even an episode of causing the sun's heat from excessive exposure to the sun, especially in childhood, may be enough to cause melanoma in these patients. Epidemiological data seems to reinforce the view that the reduction in sun exposure should go so far as to prevent sunburn, especially in childhood. What should be emphasised to parents of young children is to protect them from the intense sun exposure during the summer months. Children and people with light skin should use creams with a protective index of at least 10 or higher according to the sun's intensity.

Ewing Sarcoma

Ewing Sarcoma is the second most frequent malignant bone tumour in adolescents and young adults. The majority of Ewing sarcoma develops in bones; however 15-20% of Ewing sarcoma originates in the soft tissue surrounding bones [10-11]. When first reported by James Ewing, in his first reports in 1921, proposed an endothelial origin for the sarcoma based on its cellular morphology and rareness of stroma. In 1971 a myelogenous origin of Ewing sarcoma was proposed given ultrastructural features resembling developing myelocytes. Since then, several hypotheses regarding the histogenesis of Ewing sarcoma have been expressed, with neural crest cells and mesenchymal stem cells receiving the most attention as the putative cells of origin. For Ewing sarcoma, the 5-year survival rate has increased over the same time from 59% to 78% for children younger than 15 years and from 20% to 60% in adolescents aged 15 to 19 years. Patients with Ewing sarcoma in the distal extremities have the best prognosis [12-15].

Neuroblastoma

The second most common tumour in this group, called neuroblastoma, is characterised by a heterogeneous clinical behaviour, ranging from spontaneous regression to aggressive and inoperable disease [16]. Fifty per cent of cases are considered high risk, with long-term survival rates after multimodal chemo- and immunotherapy below 40% [17]. Neuroblastoma can develop either sporadically or be transmitted in the germline. If a tumour involves the spinal cord, cord compression or paralysis may be seen. Diagnostic evaluation relies not only on a careful history and physical examination, but also on biochemical, histologic, and radiographic analyses. Histologic confirmation is required to establish a diagnosis of neuroblastoma [18].

Leukaemia

Leukaemia is the most common malignant disease in children. It affects children of the white race rather than black. It may occur at any age, but 50% of children are aged 0-5 years. Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) is the most frequent cancer among children. Current risk-adapted treatments and supportive care have increased the survival rate to over 90% in the developed countries. However, approximately 20% of children who relapse have a poor prognosis, making leukaemia the leading cause of cancer mortality in pediatric disorders. Feature selection usually plays a significant role in machine learning, as irrelevant attributes may lead to low accuracy, less interpreted and over-fitting results in classification analysis. The prognosis of a child with malignant disease depends on: the histological type, the degree of differentiation, the characteristics of the biological behaviour, the extent of a tumour, the general condition of the child. Treatment depends on the type of leukaemia. However, mainly treatment is chemotherapy. The prediction of relapse in childhood acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) is a critical factor for successful treatment and follow-up planning [19].

Malignant Lymphomas

Malignant lymphomas belong to the group of systemic diseases and are divided into two groups: a. Hodgkin's disease or Hodgkin's lymphoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma. Lymphoma is one of the most common cancers in adolescent and young adults. The treatment of malignant lymphoma is dependent on the type of lymphoma. Hodgkin's disease in children is usually treated with a combination of chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Non-Hodgkin lymphoma is mainly treated with chemotherapy. Both treatment and prognosis of pediatric non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL) have improved dramatically in the last 30 years. Currently, localized or limited-stage NHL (stage I to II) has an approximately 95%-100% 5-year event-free survival (EFS) rate.

Furthermore, the prognosis for children with advanced-stage disease (stage III to IV) has doubled from approximately 40% 5-year EFS 30 years ago to more than 80%. Hodgkin lymphoma is also known to have around 80% 10-year EFS rate. Hodgkin Lymphoma is curable in more than 90% of cases. Even though children have good outcomes when treated with risk-adapted strategies, adolescents who are between 15 and 18 years old seem to experience poorer survival rates, whereas patients older than 18 years old have globally the same outcome than older adults. This category of patients needs particular care, based on tight coordination between adults and pediatric oncologists. In conclusion, adolescent and young adults' lymphomas are curable diseases but require personalized management in onco-haematological units [20].

Rhabdomyosarcoma (RMS)

Rhabdomyosarcoma is a highly malignant tumour in children and is characterized by a high recurrence rate and presence of metastases [21-22]. It originates from immature striated muscles and is mainly found in the head, neck, extremities and genitourinary system [23]. Although multimodal therapy including wide excision, radiotherapy, and dose-intensive chemotherapy is used to treat RMS, those ways of treatment are not available for RMS patients with relapse or distant metastases [24]. Childhood rhabdomyosarcoma is a soft tissue malignant tumour of mesenchymal origin. It accounts for approximately 3.5% of the cases of cancer among children aged 0 to 14 years and 2% of the cases among adolescents and young adults aged 15 to 19 years [25-26]. All children with rhabdomyosarcoma should receive chemotherapy. The intensity and duration of the chemotherapy are dependent on the Risk Group assignment [27].

Intracranial tumours

As presenting symptoms are considered the following: a headache (31%), vomiting (31%), seizures (21%), and behavioural change (11%). The most prevalent symptoms in this diagnosis were a headache (51%), vomiting (51%), visual difficulties (37%), seizures (24%), and behavioural change (21%). A headache and vomiting are the earliest and most prevalent symptoms in children with brain tumours. Visual symptoms and behavioural change are often present. Abnormalities in the neurological examination are reported in most of the children [28].

The most common brain tumour in children is the astrocytoma. Surgical tumour exclusion is the primary therapeutic approach. Total resection should be achieved as these tumours often recur rapidly [29].

Psychosocial Aspects of children and adolescent cancer diagnosis

The diagnosis of cancer is a traumatic event that puts children and adolescents at an increased risk for adjustment problems and adverse psychological outcomes [30-31]. It can be disruptive to emotional and may have detrimental effects on the cognitive and social development of the individual, a process by which young people develop self-views, social cognition, awareness, and emotional well-being [32]. Coping with the disease presents new challenges: the diagnosis phase, the phase of treatment and the post-treatment or remission phase [33-34].

Developmental perspective

In infants and preschoolers, emotion self-regulation becomes understandable from a dyadic perspective because the primary caregiver is central to providing regulation that a small child needs. For example, maternal depression can lead to emotional distress in preschoolers and results in externalised symptoms such as aggressive behaviour [35]. On the other hand, young patients of pre-school age rarely experience hair loss or weight gain as a major problem [36]. In children, coping with a cancer diagnosis varies, depending on the child's temperament and coping style [35]. They are often annoyed by physical changes as those affect their image to others. For preadolescent children, frequent hospitalisations, invasive medical procedures, and physical symptoms are associated with significant distress. Cancer has adverse impacts on behavioural, emotional and social aspects as well as in their learning development and well-being [37-39].

Current studies have shown that it is directly linked to isolation from family members and missed opportunities in school and peer activities [40-41]. During adolescence, individuals are trying to develop their identity and independence from their parents, while peer relationships become their predominant activities. Cancer therapy often requires increased dependence from parents and social isolation from peers, which can challenge their need for autonomy. Adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer frequently face the loss of their body image, sexuality, fertility and their imagined future in general [42].

Emotional distress and psychosocial considerations

Children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer are at risk of depression due to disruptions in their developmental trajectory and the tremendous physical symptom burden they suffer [42]. They experience emotional distress such as post-traumatic stress symptoms, anxiety [43], obsessive-compulsive disorders [43-45], sadness, irritability [35] and the perpetual fear of recurrence [34]. Late adolescents are at higher risk for severe depression within the first year following a cancer diagnosis. It is challenging to estimate with accuracy the incidence of depressive disorders because the co-occurrence of physical symptoms such as fatigue, anorexia, and sleep disruption are frequent in both diagnoses [42, 46]. What is for sure is that the interruptions in expected life roles, body image perception and peer relations are significant sources of psychological and existential concern and contribute to depression.

Cancer has also been described as a potential moderator of school life as it disrupts the educational process due to absenteeism and poor performance in tests [47-50]. Illness uncertainty surrounding the severity, the treatment and prognosis are identified as another significant stressor for children with a cancer diagnosis [43].

Family system and its functioning comprise a crucial role in the emotional distress in pediatric cancer [35]. Parental involvement during treatment may complicate the natural progression towards independence. Disruptions in family routines and relationships and parental work-life changes [51] are potential risk factors for maladjustment [39]. A cancer experience may also include a higher risk of social isolation, and late adolescents often report missing out on critical social activities during their treatment. Thus, the consequences of cancer on relationships with parents, siblings and peers may manifest the need for support, while healthy relationships are a key component of well-being [47].

Psychotherapeutic interventions

Children with cancer spend a period using intensive multimodal therapies with transient and milder side effects. They have much stress due to the unknown hospital environment and the different faces of nursing and medical staff which seem unfamiliar to them. Recent surveys have shown that cortisol levels were lower among children who were able to receive further information regarding the operation and process in comparison to children who were unprepared. Also, the absence of familiar persons multiplied the problematic behaviour with symptoms such as crying, dystopia and lack of tendency to explore. On the contrary, the presence of intimate persons has had positive effects such as a tendency for exploration (asking questions, approaching organs, etc.), a reduction in self-centred and escape tendencies

(such as running towards the exit or having actions of panic attacks). In conclusion, the younger the patient, the more intense the behavioural problems were (crying, food denial, protests, regressions, etc.).

The general approach is to talk to the child about the illness. At an early age, the child is better acquainted with the adult world by playing toys, doll rolls (for example, doctor, nurse, patient), special toys such as plastic medical instruments, injections. Puppet theatre also enables us to play everything that's happening. This method is called gynaecology therapy and is applied by special pediatric psychologists and other specialised staff. Gaming therapy helps the child overcome his unpleasant feelings and fears of being admitted to the hospital [52].

Cognitive behaviour therapy (CBT) provided via the Internet is a promising treatment modality for a range of conditions, increasing access to support for parents of children who are receiving treatment for cancer [53-55]. Research has reported that less than half of parents who report a need to see a psychologist have had the opportunity to take part in this.

Most adolescents respond well enough because they have great adaptability [56]. Literature suggests that children and adolescents with a cancer diagnosis demonstrate comparable or lower levels of distress about those without a history of serious illness. It is evidenced that children with cancer do not differ from healthy ones with regards to psychological functioning — problems that those experience may become better attributed to factors other than cancer, such as stressful life events and family dysfunctional environment [57]. It is essential that a physician's empathetic attitude can also have a positive influence on psychological adjustments giving opportunities to discuss feelings about the newly diagnosed cancer patients [35]. Adolescent support groups have been proven to increase cooperation between peers and with their therapists [58].

Conclusion

While diseases in childhood are mainly described as common incidents in the early stages of children's life, cancer incidents cannot be attributed as facts directly related to the child and teenager; a certain variety of neoplasms dominate in childhood. The day of diagnosing cancer in this young population has always been a painful day for both patients and their families.

It is apparent that the occurrence of cancer in a child is a traumatic experience and carries significant impacts on both patients and their families. Primary psychological and social support should focus more on the emotional relief of those patients and families rather than the health consequences of the disease and its treatment. Moreover, palliative care for pediatric patients is confronted with many challenges, which can include cost, availability, and timing of referrals. It is of great importance to have a comprehensive and meaningful psychological intervention in those cases, which will improve the quality of life for those patients. Last but not least, we should always bear in mind that psychological care for children and adolescents with cancer has particularities that require: knowledge, clinical experience, ongoing education, sensitivity, humanity, and above all courage and courage.

Conflict of Interest

None

Funding

None

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